

Synthesis and Anti-inflammatory Activity of a Series of β -Aminoxypropionic Acids

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Arylacetic acids are a well-known potent class of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs¹. Mechanism of action of adrenergic drugs² show that the (methyleneaminoxy)methyl moiety can be considered as a 'bio-isostere' of an aryl group (Ar)³. A series of β -aminoxypropionic acids (AOPAs) were synthesised⁴ and evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity.

In continuation to our work on the synthesis of anti-inflammatory agents⁵, we directed our efforts towards the use of substituted-benzaldehydes, such as anisaldehyde, piperonal, veratraldehyde and 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes with a view to study the effect of changes in the substitution pattern on the anti-inflammatory activity. In the alkyl substituted benzaldehydes the ethyl and propyl chains are flexible and large number of conformers are possible. Efforts have been made to prepare the restricted conformers of the compounds, as restricting the number of conformers may result in enhancing activity. AOPAs (**4a-m**) were prepared (Scheme 1) by Michael-type reaction of the appropriate aldoximes and ketoximes of substituted-benzaldehydes, indanones and tetralone with ethyl acrylate (**2**) followed by alkaline hydrolysis of the ethyl esters (**3**).

All the compounds (Table 1) were tested for anti-inflammatory activity by the carrageenan oedema test model in rats⁶. Compounds were freshly prepared as a fine homogenised suspension in gum acacia (2%, w/v) in normal saline. Male albino Charles Foster rats (120–160 g body weight) in groups of five were used. The test compounds were administered at 100 mg/kg orally 45 min or intraperitoneally 30 min before the carrageenan injection. The inflammation was induced by injecting 0.1 ml of carrageenan (0.1 ml; 1%, w/v) solution in normal saline into

the subplanter region of the left hind paw of the rat. In every experiment, one group was used as a control and given only vehicle, i.e. 2% gum acacia suspension whilst another group received a standard drug ibuprofen for the comparison of the activity. Paw volume was measured im-

TABLE I—CHEMICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF β -AMINOXYPROPIONIC ACID (**4a-m**)*

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	M p** °C	% Inhibn. 3.5 h
4a		—	61–63 ^u	18.49
b	(4-OMe)C ₆ H ₄ -	H	48–49 ^c	28.30, 28.57 ^g
c	(3-OMe, 4-OMe)C ₆ H ₃ -	H	70–71 ^d	18.86, 38.57 ^g
d	(3,4-OCH ₂ O-)C ₆ H ₃ -	H	37–39 ^e	30.06, 33.57 ^g
e	(2-OMe, 4-OMe, 5-Et)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	66–68 ^b	8.49
f	(2-OMe, 4-OMe, 5-Pr)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	Oil ^f	32.15, 26.42 ^g
g	(2-OEt, 4-OMe, 5-Et)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	62–65 ^c	14.52
h	(2-OEt, 4-OMe, 5-Pr)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	84–86 ^d	5.66, 35.24 ^g
i	(2-OEt, 4-OEt, 5-Et)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	70–73 ^b	11.96
j	(2-OEt, 4-OEt, 5-Pr)C ₆ H ₂ -	H	Oil ^f	20.51, 28.73 ^g
k		—	100 ^e	18.23, 20.09 ^g
l		—	80 ^e	25.17
m		—	92–93 ^e	13.95, 16.28 ^g

*All compound gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 43–82%; compound showed similar spectral data as described for representative compound in experimental section

Solvent for crystallisation : ^uEt₂O, ^bbenzene-petroleum ether, ^cCHCl₃, ^dAcOEt, ^epetroleum ether, ^fpurified by column chromatography on silica gel : 1 : 1 benzene-AcOEt (4f**); 4 : 1 AcOEt-hexane (**4j**)

ml), pentyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (3.3 g) in dry DMSO (10 ml) was added for 15 min at 15–20° under N₂ atmosphere. After stirring for 30 min at room temperature, the solution was cooled and methyl azelaldehyde (0.74 g) in dry THF (5 ml) was added dropwise for 1 min at 15°. The mixture was stirred for 10 h at room temperature, then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent gave **5** as a liquid (0.44 g). The product was purified by column chromatography over silica gel : (Found : C, 74.80; H, 11.62. C₁₅H₂₈O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.00; H, 11.66%); ν_{\max} 1 740, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 3.65 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 5.28 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-9-Tetradecen-1-ol (**6**) : Compound **5** (0.4 g) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride (0.18 g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) at room temperature for 24 h. On usual workup, the alcohol was obtained as a liquid, which was purified by distillation (0.28 g), b.p. 122–126°/0.08 mm (lit.⁷ 120–125°/0.08 mm) (Found : C, 79.69; H, 13.14. C₁₄H₂₈O calcd. for : C, 79.24; H, 13.20%); ν_{\max} 3 205, 2 920, 2 840, 1 435, 1 175, 725 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.86 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.26 (16H, br, CH₂), 1.9 (4H, br, CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 3.42 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.3 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-9-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**7**) : Acetic anhydride (5.0 ml) was added to a solution **6** (0.2 g) in pyridine (5.0 ml) and stirred for 1 h and kept at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with cold dil. HCl, water, aq. NaHCO₃ (5%) and water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent yielded **7** (0.18 g) as a colourless liquid. The crude product on purification by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°)-ether (80 : 20, v/v) as eluent afforded the product (tlc, single spot) (0.144 g), (Found : C, 75.38; H, 12.00. C₁₆H₃₀O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.59; H, 11.81%); ν_{\max} 2 920, 2 840, 1 725, 1 435, 1 230, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.86 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.26 (16H, br, CH₂), 1.9 (4H, br, CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, -O-CO-CH₃), 4.06 (2H, br, CH₂-OAc), 5.31 (2H, t, CH=CH).

(Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-ol (**8**) : Sodium hydride (0.2 g, 50% dispersion in oil) in dry DMSO (10 ml) was stirred under N₂ atmosphere for 1 h, followed by addition of heptyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (4.1 g) in dry DMSO (10 ml) for 15 min at 15–20°. After stirring for 30 min at room temperature, the solution was cooled and then treated dropwise with 7-hydroxyheptanal (**2**; 2.64 g) in dry THF (10 ml). The mixture was stirred for 10 h at room temperature, poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether, washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent removal gave **8** as liquid residue (1.4 g), which was purified chromatographically over neutral alumina (tlc, single spot) : (Found : C, 79.20; H, 13.13. C₁₄H₂₈O calcd. for : C, 79.24;

H, 13.20%); ν_{\max} 3 425, 2 930, 2 875, 1 040, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.91 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.31 (16H, m, saturated CH₂), 2.08 (4H, m, allylic protons), 3.59 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.48–5.60 (2H, m, CH=CH).

(Z)-7-Tetradecen-1-yl acetate (**9**) : Compound **8** (0.5 g) was stirred with pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. To it little water was added and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed successively with cold dil. HCl, water, NaHCO₃ (5%), water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent removal and purification of the crude product over neutral alumina gave **9** (0.34 g) (Found : C, 75.52; H, 11.80. C₁₆H₃₀O₂ calcd. for : C, 75.59; H, 11.81%); ν_{\max} 2 952, 2 880, 1 740, 1 240, 1 035, 730 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.94 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.36 (16H, m, saturated CH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, COCH₃), 2.16 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.94 (2H, t, -CH₂-O-CO-), 5.43–5.66 (2H, m, CH=CH).

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